

Supplementary Material 2

Characteristics of the developed microsatellite loci

Allegue H., Guinet C., Patrick S.C., Ribout C., Bichet C., Lepais O., Réale D.. *Offspring sex ratio increases with paternal reproductive success in a colony of southern elephant seals.*

Table S1: Characteristics of the developed microsatellite loci. The loci in bold (N=36) were selected for the paternity assignment analyses.

Locus name	Read ID ¹	SSR motif	Number of repeats	Amplicon size	Forward primer sequence ²	Reverse primer sequence ³	Mean reads per sample	Analysis strategy	Parameter set ⁴	Number of haplotypes	Number of alleles by size	Missing data rate	Allelic error rate	Probability of Hardy-Weinberg proportion after correction with False Discovery Rates	Allele null frequency
SSRseqMir_001	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:21951:16234	CT	24	175	GTAAGTCCCCTGCAAGAAGGGA	ATGGCACCTGCTTACGGAAGAGGCT	102	failed							
SSRseqMir_002	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:17113:24727	TG	19	159	AGGCTAGTCACTATGATCAGATGGT	ATGCAAGGTCAAGTTCTCGAAAGCT	93	FullLength	PS1	20	10	0.116	0.018	0.0004	0.1000
SSRseqMir_003	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:20504:6299	AC	19	173	AACACAAGGTGACGTTGCCCTCACC	TCTCCTTGACAGTCCGTCAAATATGA	0	failed							
SSRseqMir_004	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:11266:8587	CT	17	161	GGTGTCTCTGGAGAGTCTTCCTC	GGCAGATGGGCAGATGCTGACAGGT	259	failed							
SSRseqMir_005	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:15025:28392	AC	16	110	ACTACCTGGGCAGAAACAGCAGCCT	AGTGTGGATGCAGTCAGAAGCCCT	336	failed							
SSRseqMir_006	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:5895:19332	CA	16	147	CCAGTGTGCTGTCTCCTTCCCACCT	CCTGGCCAAGTGGAGTTGTGGTCT	153	failed							
SSRseqMir_007	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:11475:6529	GT	16	177	TCCACTGAGTTGGGAAGCTGCCACT	AGAGCTGAACCATGACTCCTGGGCC	93	failed							
SSRseqMir_008	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:22470:14014	AC	16	179	TTGTCTCCCAGGGACCTCCAAGCC	TCTGATATAAACCCGGCTCACACCA	155	RepeatFocused	PS2	9	9	0.128	0.039	0.8438	0.0078
SSRseqMir_009	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:15931:12883	CA	15	139	TTTGCTTCTCTTCTGCATCTGTG	TGCTCCAGTGGGCAGAGATAAAGTGT	180	failed							
SSRseqMir_010	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:21522:18636	TG	15	143	GCAAAGTGAATTCAAATTCCTCCCA	CCACCCAGGCACCCTACAAATGAAT	71	FullLength	PS1	15	8	0.357	0.000	0.5675	-0.0009
SSRseqMir_011	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:12195:11140	AC	15	147	CCAGCGGTGCTTCTGAAGAGCCAA	ACAGGTGGGCGAATTTGCAAAGACA	161	failed							
SSRseqMir_012	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:13863:17955	GT	15	133	ACTCCAAAGATGAATAACCATGGGT	TCCAGACAAGGACAAAGCTGAGGGC	177	RepeatFocused	PS1	21	10	0.045	0.000	0.8438	-0.0055
SSRseqMir_013	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:20665:12801	AC	15	117	CCTACGCTAATGACTGGAGTGATGG	GGCTCTAGTTGGTGAGTGGTGAGGG	0	failed							
SSRseqMir_014	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:20763:11689	TG	15	156	GATGGGAAATTTGCACCTGTCTGGG	TGGTAGCTGATCTTGTCTGTCCCA	4	failed							
SSRseqMir_015	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:21928:5952	AC	15	171	AGTGAGGCTTAAGTGGGAGAAGTTGG	TGAGACAGCAAGACCCTGTAGGCC	196	FullLength	PS1	8	5	0.088	0.005	0.8438	-0.0114

SSRseqMir_048	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:4283:9109	GAAT	11	143	ATTGTGAGTTTCCTTATTGCCAGGT	TGACCACAGCCTCATGCAAGCTTCC	246	FullLength	PS1	11	7	0.041	0.000	0.8438	-0.0095
SSRseqMir_049	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:13868:15874	ATCT	10	180	GAAGACTCAGGCCTCTTCAAGGAG	GCAAACCAAGGATCCTAATAACTCCT	0	failed							
SSRseqMir_050	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:24406:6129	ATAG	10	150	ACGTATGTGGTGCTGGAATGTGAAC	AAGCAAATTACCCAACCTGTCTGGA	316	FullLength	PS1	15	9	0.056	0.005	0.8438	-0.0075
SSRseqMir_051	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:9640:7787	TTG	9	178	TGATCTGGTAGCCTGTGACCTTGCT	TCAGCTCCATTCAACTGGAATCTT	72	RepeatFocused	PS1	4	4	0.292	0.000	0.8438	0.0248
SSRseqMir_052	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:20353:17077	AAC	8	137	GGCAGAATGACTGGATGAATTTACCC	GGGATTGGTGCCCTTCATTGCTGACA	361	FullLength	PS1	5	4	0.041	0.000	0.8438	-0.0009
SSRseqMir_053	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:14517:26784	AAC	7	170	TGACATTGGCAGTCATTTGGGTACT	GTCCAATATGTTTCAGAGTAGGACCCA	45	FullLength	PS1	6	3	0.182	0.000	0.8438	-0.0240
SSRseqMir_054	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:18189:13439	AAC	7	139	GCAAATTAAGCCACAATGAGATGCC	CCACCCTGGATGCATGAGCTTTGGG	397	FullLength	PS1	2	1	0.042	0.000	0.8238	0.0269
SSRseqMir_055	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:18956:17720	TTG	7	125	GCACTGCCTTTGCTTCCTCCCATACA	ACCAAGAGTCAAAGAAGTCACAGGG	378	FullLength	PS1	4	2	0.041	0.000	0.9635	-0.0164
SSRseqMir_056	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:25344:24966	CAC	7	121	AGTTCAGGGATCTAAGGGACCGCA	GGTTGGTTAATACACCCTTTACCTCA	483	FullLength	PS1	3	3	0.037	0.000	0.8438	-0.0198
SSRseqMir_057	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:7483:17314	CAC	7	119	ACAAGAGATTGACAAGAAGTTCCC	AGGGCTTGAAACATTATGCATGCC	494	FullLength	PS1	1	1	0.035	0.000	NA	NA
SSRseqMir_058	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1102:19375:13167	ACA	7	180	CATACACCATGCAGGAACAGACATT	CATCAGTCTCTGAGTCTTGGGTTT	115	RepeatFocused	PS2	12	7	0.131	0.000	0.9875	-0.0079
SSRseqMir_059	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:10614:9043	AAC	6	155	AGCATCATCTGCTGCTTATGTTGT	GAAACCGCAGCATGATATTGTTTCA	145	FullLength	PS1	3	2	0.354	0.000	0.8233	0.0347
SSRseqMir_060	M01328:337:000000000-D7MCL:1:1101:12109:5500	TTC	6	155	CCTATCCCAAACGTGCTTCTTCGCA	GACTGCTCTGCTGGTGGACTA	544	FullLength	PS1	1	1	0.037	0.000	NA	NA
Overall							204			368	257	0.108	0.007		

¹ Read identification number in the publicly available DNA sequences (European Nucleotide Archive accession number ERR10752787) generated from a random shotgun sequencing of a DNA pool of 10 individuals.

² the universal Illumina adapter overhang sequences TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG was added to the 5' end of the forward primers;

³ the universal Illumina adapter overhang sequences GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG was added to the 5' end of the reverse primers;

⁴ FDSTools parameters as followed: PS1 corresponds to -s-1=50,+1=10 -m=15 -n=20 and PS2 corresponds to -s-1=70,+1=10 -m=10 -n=20.